

*Editorial Desk***Five States Leading Deceased Donation and Transplantation in India**

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India's deceased organ donation program has seen significant success primarily in five states - Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Telangana, Maharashtra, and Gujarat. Over the past three years, each of these states has consistently recorded more than 100 donations annually. In 2024 alone, they collectively contributed 909 deceased donations, accounting for nearly 75% of the country's total donor numbers.

Tamil Nadu led the efforts with a record-breaking 268 donations, marking an all-time high. Although the state experienced a temporary decline in numbers over the past few years, it has now regained its top position. A key factor in this resurgence has been the increased participation of government

medical colleges, with a significant number of institutions contributing to the program. Additionally, a policy implemented by the state government to honour deceased donors by the district administration has significantly contributed to enhancing public engagement and awareness.

Since the inception of the deceased donation program, these five states from southern and western India have consistently advanced, while other regions have struggled to maintain momentum. This trend extends to eye donations as well, where these states continue to lead the country.

State honors for organ donors in Tamil Nadu - A top government official (IAS) from the Thiruvannamalai District carries a wreath during the last rites of an organ donor.

**India - 2024
States with highest
deceased organ donation**

Source :
<https://www.notto.mohfw.gov.in/>
<https://censusindia.gov.in/census.website/data/census-tables>

States with highest number of deceased donations

States / Year	2022	2023	2024
Tamil Nadu	156	178	268
Telangana	194	200	188
Maharashtra	105	148	172
Karnataka	151	178	162
Gujarat	148	146	119

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